

BBioNets

Boosting the adoption
of Bio-Based Technologies

Cross-Fertilisation Meetings

Bio-Based Practices on Farms & Forests

Accelerating “Bio-Based Practices on Farms and Forests”

Key Takeaways

CFM No6 “Opportunities in Green Biorefineries”

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The sixth and last BBioNets Cross-Fertilisation Meeting focused on advancing circular bioeconomy solutions in the context of biomass utilisation and integrating innovative processing approaches into agricultural systems, with particular attention given to green biorefineries and sustainable energy production. The invited speakers from Ireland, Poland, and the Czech Republic presented topics including the development of rural green biorefineries in Ireland, the technical potential of permanent grasslands in Poland, and the construction and operation of biomethane plants based on the Czech case.

The first presentation from Ireland exploring the concept of rural green biorefineries focused on grasslands as the abundant and untapped source of protein. It outlined how grass can be converted into multiple valuable products, including leaf protein concentrate, fibre-rich animal feed, and other bio-based products. The speaker presented promising results of conducted trials and pilot projects advancing technology scale-up.

Then, based on the methodology used to estimate the technical potential of grasslands in Poland, we learned how the biomass availability and use can vary across regions. Taking into account the competing demand between livestock feed and energy production, the expert showed how environmental constraints, logistical limitations, and policy requirements can limit the amount of available biomass surplus.

The last presentation provided an overview of the construction and operation of a biomethane plant, including the technologies used in plants of different scales, choice of feedstock and its performance, as well as a range of environmental and economic benefits. The speaker discussed also the development of the biomethane sector in the Czech Republic, outlining current capacity and future expansion possibilities.

The webinar aimed to highlight both research developments and practical applications, demonstrating how agricultural residues and other underutilised resources can be valorised for energy and bio-based products, in line with circular bioeconomy and the zero waste principle. Although presentations focused on country-based contexts, presenters discussed also the transferability and adaptability of technologies and methodologies across regions. The Q&A session allowed for exchange between experts and participants, fostering a discussion on challenges, scalability, and policy implications.

Overall, the discussion underlined the importance of integrated, circular approach in strengthening rural bioeconomy systems, while emphasizing that long term, targeted policy is essential for the successful scalability and deployment of such solutions in rural areas.

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Development of rural green biorefinery research in Ireland

Presenter: *James Gaffey - Co-director, [Circular Bioeconomy Cluster Research Group](#), Munster Technological University (Ireland)*

- **Grasslands as a resource of sustainable protein.** The presentation focused on the potential of grasslands as a sustainable and highly underused protein source. Grasslands cover large areas in Europe (20% of total land area on average, with even 60% in Ireland) yet Europe imports ~ 17 million tonnes of protein every year (mainly soybean feed). While soy is rich in protein, grass offers higher protein yield per hectare and supports local protein production thus reducing its carbon footprint.
- **Green biorefineries as an efficient circular use of grass.** Green biorefineries convert grass into multiple valuable streams: leaf protein concentrate (~43% protein, comparable to soybean meal), fibre rich press cake (silage replacement and feed for ruminants), brown juice (for bioenergy, fertilisers, biochemicals). Trials show these can substitute silage and soybean meal in cow and pig's diet with similar or improved results.
- **Pilot demonstrations and upscaling.** Pilot projects like Farm Zero C are advancing technology scale-up, including decentralised models with on-farm pressing of grass and centralised processing of juice. Alternative feedstocks like clover, duckweed, cover-crops are tested to extend production beyond the grass-growing season. To become commercially viable, green biorefineries must integrate high-value co-products, e.g. prebiotics, bio-based materials, food additives, and diversify feedstocks.

Discussion key takeaways

- **Policy and market barriers:** the key challenge are regulatory and market constraints (e.g. strict and costly regulations on novel food approval), which slow down commercialisation of grass-based products. Shifting the perception of grass from solely a forage crop to a recognised protein source within EU policy would help unlock funding and accelerate market growth.
- **Scalability and transferability:** the biorefinery technology is highly transferable across countries (already implemented in Denmark, Sweden, and the Netherlands). Relatively low complexity of the process and adaptability to different grass types make it suitable for regional or farm-based deployment. Key conditions for success are availability of grassland resources, collaboration with farmers and scaling at regional, not overly centralised level.
- **End use and processing limitations:** separating contaminants such as plastics, metals, stones from grass biomass remains a major technical bottleneck. This is especially critical for roadside and landscaping grass representing an additional biomass source. Effective pre-treatment is essential for higher-value uses of this biomass. Solutions deployed at demonstration and pilot scale include industrial pre-washing and sensor-based detection technologies.

Balancing Feed Demand and Energy Supply: Technical Potential of Permanent Grassland Biomass in Poland

Presenter: *Magdalena Borzęcka – Associate Professor, [Institute of Soil Science and Plant Cultivation – State Research Institute](#) (Poland)*

- **Grassland resources across Europe.** The presentation focused on the technical potential of grasslands based on the example of Poland. Permanent grasslands in EU cover ca. 50 million ha with average utilisation rate of 31%. In recent years, grassland area has changed, increasing mostly in the Mediterranean region (in Spain by 27%), while decreasing in Baltic countries (by 33% in Lithuania). This shows that availability of grasslands is dynamic and differs between regions.

- **Theoretical vs. technical potential of grasslands.** The primary use of grassland biomass is livestock feed (as hay, silage, grazing) which must be satisfied before energy use. In Poland, theoretical potential of hay amounted to ca. 15 million tonnes in 2024 but after accounting for livestock demand, drought losses, political constraints, the remaining biomass resource is negligible at the national level. However, at municipality level, areas with biomass surplus can be identified showing the importance of detailed spatial analyses.
- **Benefits and limitations of utilising grassland biomass.** Grasslands offer environmental and strategic benefits: lowering GHG emissions compared to energy crops, supporting carbon sequestration, biodiversity, soil protection, contribution to EU biomethane targets. On the other hand, several constraints reduce the usability of biomass: late mowing required by eco-schemes can reduce the biogas yield, low density leads to high transport cost, storage losses can reach 30%, proving the theoretical estimates exceed the real biomass surplus.

Discussion key takeaways

- **Key barriers to wider use of permanent grassland biomass:** the main challenges remain environmental, logistical, and technological - a key issue is regional variability of biomass available. This makes it necessary to carry out detailed analyses at the local and regional level to effectively identify viable areas for investment.
- **Regulatory and economic constraints:** the most critical barriers are uncertainty of energy markets, insufficient policy stability, lack of long-term contracts, which combined together discourage farmers and investors from committing. High upfront capital requirements for technologies such as biogas plants and related infrastructure further slow down their deployment.
- **Transferability of the methodology:** the methodology for estimation of available biomass can be transferred to other EU countries but current EU-wide datasets (e.g. NUTS level) are too aggregated to capture true local biomass potential. For improving the accuracy of estimates, region-specific data are needed. The approach could be expanded beyond permanent grasslands to include other biomass resources (roadside and marginal land vegetation) and match them with the most suitable technologies for effective utilisation.

Experience with the construction and operation of biomethane stations

Presenter: **Ondřej Frič** – Chief Sales Officer for CZ+SK, [AgriKomp Bohemia s.r.o.](#) (Czech Republic)

- **Biomethane trend in Europe.** Biomethane is gaining popularity in the European energy sector. The trend is strongest in the Western Europe, where production has reached 5.2 billion cubic metres. Smaller plants typically use membrane separation technology, while larger facilities use alternatives such as chemical absorption or water scrubbing.
- **Benefits of biomethane production.** Biomethane offers environmental benefits and stable income for farmers, as many plants are farm-based. Performance depends on the feedstock choice: energy crops, waste, or manure, with manure achieving the highest carbon savings, followed by waste-based feedstocks. Biogas and biomethane production also generates valuable fertiliser, contributing to GHG reduction.
- **Development of the Biomethane Sector in the Czech Republic.** The Czech biomethane sector is emerging but has strong growth potential. There are about 600 biogas and 13 biomethane plants. The aim is reach 500 million cubic metres of biomethane by 2030 from 20 million today. Growth is expected from modernisation or conversion of existing biogas plants, support from subsidies, along with new projects: CO2 liquefaction enabling the use of residual CO2 for industrial applications.

Discussion key takeaways

- **Future development and 2030 perspective.** The sector is expected to expand gradually. The ambitious target of producing 500 million cubic meters largely depends on the successful support from operational subsidies for new projects (2027-2030). A part of the input is also expected to come from the modernisation of biogas stations but many will not be able to convert to biomethane production.
- **Infrastructure and technical constraints**, such as insufficient gas grid infrastructure, are the major challenge in connecting new plants to high pressure networks where capacity exists. Solving technical barriers by e.g. enabling reverse flow compression is planned to accelerate sector development and move closer to national targets.
- **Transferability and the role of policy.** The biomethane technology itself is mature and widely used in Western Europe. Examples from Slovakia and the Czech Republic, with emerging projects in Poland prove transferability across countries. Technology adoption is already underway but wider deployment depends on supportive national policies and financial incentives to scale up effectively.

[Download the presentations](#)

[Watch the recording](#)

What are Cross-Fertilisation Meetings?

BBioNets' **Cross-Fertilisation Meetings** are essential events designed to connect the project's regional **Forest and Agriculture Networks (FANs)**. While each FAN addresses unique **regional realities and specific challenges**, there is significant common ground regarding biomass availability, exploitation potential, and shared needs. By networking across borders, the project aims to collectively increase the impact of local work significantly.

These meetings were designed to help participants:

- **Share Difficulties:** Exchange common challenges and concerns regarding the application and scaling of **Bio-Based Technologies (BBTs)**.
- **Discover Opportunities:** Outline new breakthroughs, emerging technologies, and potential market opportunities across regions.
- **Promote Knowledge:** Capture, validate, and widely promote practical knowledge created by national EIP-AGRI Operational Groups (OGs).
- **Forge Collaborations:** Facilitate bilateral and multilateral collaboration opportunities among FANs and OGs.

The Six-Part Series: Topics and Schedule

1. **Innovations in Nutrient Recovery:** 11 December 2025
2. **Innovative Hemp Practices:** 15 January 2026
3. **Sustainable Sheep Wool Processing:** 29 January 2026
4. **Efficient Woody Biomass Utilisation:** 12 February 2026
5. **Circular Approaches in Olive Groves:** 26 February 2026
6. **Opportunities in Green Biorefineries:** 23 April 2026

BBioNets Project Identity

Full Project Title	BBioNets – Creation and promotion of Forest and Agriculture Networks to boost Bio-Based Technologies adoption and Value Chain development (GA No 101133904)		
Start – end date	1/11/2023 – 31/10/2026 (36 months)		
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